

A double pricing and penalties “Separated” imbalance settlement mechanism to incentive self balancing of market parties

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Abstract—Increasing penetrations of variable renewable energy sources increase the usage and costs of reserves due to their stochastic nature. As Balance Responsible Parties all market participants pay the balancing costs of their imbalances according to the imbalance settlement mechanism of each market zone. The European balancing markets and the imbalance settlement mechanisms still have different rules across Europe, but normally, the prices of upward and downward regulation are higher and lower than spot prices, respectively, originating penalties. Against this background, this work presents an alternative “Separated” imbalance settlement mechanism that consists of unbalanced parties paying/receiving directly the costs/revenues of the balancing markets needed to balance them. In this mechanism, the net costs/revenues of Transmission System Operators with energy balancing mechanisms are zero. Furthermore, by separating the payment of penalties between unbalanced directions, this mechanism also incentive unbalanced parties to self-control their dispatch, mitigating part of their deviations. Two case studies have been presented to test the application of this mechanism in Portugal and Spain, comparing its outputs with those of the mechanisms in place in these countries during 2019. Outputs from the studies prove the benefit of using this mechanism to reduce penalties, mainly in the case of active market players that can partly control their dispatch.

Index Terms—balancing markets, balance responsible parties, imbalance prices and penalties, imbalance settlement, variable renewable energy sources.

I. INTRODUCTION

The legislation of the European Commission for regulating the European Internal Market of Electricity (EIME) encompasses measures of market design and harmonization that can motivate the integration of variable renewable energy sources (vRES) and the demand side, as well as, incentivizing their active participation in electricity markets [1]–[3].

The increasing penetration of variable renewable energy sources (vRES) across Europe is raising the usage and costs of reserves due to their low predictable generation. At the same time, the emergence of new flexible players, such as local citizen energy communities (CECs), can significantly impact balancing markets and create new opportunities [4]

As Balance Responsible Parties (BRPs) all market participants pay the balancing costs of their imbalances. The

reduction in the electricity prices, originated by the self-cannibalization effect of vRES, coupled with the increases in their imbalance costs could pose a challenge for future non-discriminatory integration of vRES into the electricity markets as active market players. Without feed-in tariffs, other incentives, or changes in the existing market design, for future investments in these sources may lack attractiveness compromising the expected decarbonization of the power systems [5]–[7]. Furthermore, providing support schemes to vRES may contribute to market distortions, increasing the incidence of negative spot prices and reducing the return of the other suppliers [8], [9].

The EIME legislation harmonized the rules of the day-ahead and intraday markets, which increased the efficient usage of cross-border trades in those markets. Notwithstanding that effort, the balancing markets and the imbalance settlement mechanisms still have different rules across Europe [2], [10]. Typically, BRPs inducing deviations pay/receive the costs/revenues of balancing markets according to the imbalance settlement mechanism of each control zone. Normally, upward and downward regulation are more costly than spot prices, resulting in penalties. Otherwise, depending on the imbalance settlement (IS) mechanism, Transmission System Operators (TSOs) may have an economic surplus or compensate BRPs [11], [12]. In Europe, the imbalance settlement mechanisms strongly differ between countries. As an example, in Nordpool countries and Spain, only those who deviate in the dominant balance direction (i.e., with a negative impact on power system operation) may pay penalties. In contrast, in Portugal, even under the same electricity market as Spain, The Iberian market of electricity (MIBEL), all unbalanced parties directly and equally pay/receive the balancing costs/revenues [12]–[14]. The mechanism used in Nordpool and Spain may be considered discriminatory since only those contributing to deviations in the dominant direction pay penalties [15], [16]. Also, unbalanced parties are not compensated independently of the balancing prices, which may originate an economic surplus for TSOs. However, if the costs of system balancing in the dominant direction are lower than those in the non-dominant

direction, TSOs may have an economic deficit [12], [17]. The Portuguese mechanism considers that all the energy balancing costs or revenues are passed to the unbalanced parties. This mechanism is perceived as fairer as it does not originate an economic surplus or deficit to TSOs. However, it does not incentivize unbalanced parties to balance themselves since they can be compensated for their imbalances [10], [11].

Against this background, this work presents an alternative imbalance settlement mechanism that consists of unbalanced parties paying/receiving directly the costs/revenues of the balancing markets needed to balance them. This mechanism consists of double penalties and pricing ensuring that the net costs/revenues of TSOs with energy balancing mechanisms are zero. It is also a fair mechanism that considers the direct payment of upward and downward energy balancing costs by up and down unbalanced parties, respectively. Furthermore, by separating the payment of penalties between unbalanced directions, this mechanism also incentivizes unbalanced parties to self-control their dispatch, mitigating some of their deviations [11].

The three aforementioned mechanisms have been modeled in the open-access Multi-agent Trading of Renewable Production (RESTRade¹) tool, developed within the scope of TradeRES project, to test their application in Portugal and Spain. The outputs of the new mechanism are compared with those from the existing mechanisms in place in these countries during 2019. RESTRade has been used to simulate the balancing markets and imbalances mechanisms in Portugal and Spain. The open-access version of this tool coupled with the Multi-Agent Simulator of Competitive Electricity Markets (MASCEM) in the Spine toolbox was used to simulate MIBEL² [18].

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section II presents an overview of wholesale and balancing electricity markets. Section III presents the imbalance mechanisms with the formulation of the new mechanism. Section IV presents two case studies. Finally, concluding remarks are presented in Section V.

II. ELECTRICITY MARKETS

Wholesale markets are composed of long-term derivative and bilateral markets, short-term marginal day-ahead and intraday markets, close to real-time continuous pay-as-bid intraday markets, and real-time ancillary services [19]. While derivatives and bilateral contracts are used for risk hedging, day-ahead markets are used as the main energy trading [20]. Intraday markets allow agents to correct potential energy deviations closer to real-time dispatch. Ancillary services solve real-time grid congestion and frequency and voltage oscillations, among other issues. Deviations from dispatch schedules are compensated in balancing markets (BMs), and the Balance-Responsible Parties (BRPs) that deviate may need to pay

the imbalance prices [21]. While the harmonization process of day-ahead and intraday markets is at an advanced stage, BMs are still in the beginning. In most European markets, BMs are mandatory and regulated by the European Network of Transmission System Operators (ENTSO-E) to guarantee the adequacy of power reserve values within each control zone. In Europe are four key types of load-frequency control products used to balance power systems. During real-time operation, the primary or frequency control reserve (FCR) is the first to be activated within a few seconds in response to frequency oscillations. Secondary or automatic-activated frequency restoration reserve (aFRR) and the Tertiary or manually-activated FRR (mFRR) are used to free up FCR and aFRR in a maximum of 15 minutes[22]. mFRR can stay active for hours.

Some BMs consider hourly or blocks of several hours to trade mFRR. The ones that consider hourly trades normally use Replacement Reserves (RRs) to deal with frequency disturbances with more than one hour, freeing up mFRR [21], [23].

A. Iberian balancing markets

Portugal and Spain participate in MIBEL, which comprises bilateral, derivatives, and spot markets. Ancillary services are independent and managed by their national TSOs. For frequency control, they consider the European balancing guidelines of the ENTSO-E with the characteristics described below [21].

All technically capable generators connected to the grid must reserve 5% of their nominal power to support FCR in stable conditions, without any remuneration. Both, Portugal and Spain, have to contribute with their FCR capacity to the meet required 3000 MW of the synchronous grid across continental Europe [22].

All technically capable players may participate in the yearly capability calls of aFRR. Therefore, they have to support aFRR throughout the year. Portugal and Spain consider day-ahead hourly marginal auctions of aFRR capacity. For historical reasons, the Portuguese TSO requires an asymmetrical aFRR capacity band with an up capacity that doubles the down capacity. It uses the ENTSO-E guidelines, upscaling the up capacity by 60% and downscaling the down capacity until 40%. So, to participate in aFRR, players must be capable to automatically respond in milliseconds and be able to offer an up capacity that doubles the down capacity. In Portugal the price of the energy players provide in aFRR is defined by the regulator or by the mFRR energy market (if cleared) due to the lack of competition. As the majority of players providing aFRR are combined cycle gas turbines, the Regulator defines the price of this service as the marginal cost of this technology [24]. As technologies providing mFRR may be different of the aFRR, receiving the clearing price of the mFRR energy market may be economically inefficient. In Spain the procurement of aFRR capacity is practically symmetrical, being their real-time balancing energy procured considering the typical pay-as-cleared mechanism of marginal markets [15], [21].

¹The user guide of the tool is available at https://traderes.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/6-TradeRES-User-Guide-RESTRade_LNEG_vf2.pdf

²This version is available at <https://github.com/TradeRES/hands-on-mascem-restrade>

In Portugal and Spain, the real-time energy used in mFRR is obtained considering a marginal hourly auction-based separate procurement of up and down regulation. However, mFRR procurement is based on hourly auctions, with RRs used for balance long-term frequency deviations exceeding one hour. RRs are cleared on a marginal market. They can be activated within 15 minutes and continue active for hours (long periods) [21], [24].

When balancing reserves obtained from competitive marginal markets are not enough to guarantee the secure operation of power systems, extraordinary reserves are acquired from bilateral agreements or in tertiary markets (e.g, as in Portugal and Spain). Furthermore, Portugal and Spain bilaterally exchange ancillary services to comply with small unbalances in their cross-border exchanges [21]–[24].

III. IMBALANCE SETTLEMENT MECHANISMS

The imbalance settlement mechanisms significantly differ among European countries. The most used mechanisms considers that BRPs only pay: i) the deviated energy is the dominant direction, ii) the net deviated energy in the dominant direction, iii) all deviated energy, and iv) directly the costs of the balancing mechanisms used to balance their unbalances [10]–[12], [14].

One aspect of the market design of wholesale, balancing, and imbalance settlement markets is the clearing period. All markets consider hourly clearings, but balancing services are counted for periods of 15 minutes, which originate up and down balancing in hourly periods. The new EIME legislation aims to harmonize the clearing periods to 15 minutes, which may contribute to increase the level of harmonization of the mechanisms used in the imbalance settlement [2], [10].

The Portuguese mechanism considers that BRPs have to equally receive/pay the hourly revenues/costs of the energy used to balance the power system [14]. Therefore, the costs of balancing energy are totally passed to BRPs, resulting in a zero cash-flow for the TSO. So, the TSO computes a single penalty, p_t^{pen} , and dual pricing, for period, t , as follows:

$$p_t^{pen} = \frac{\sum_{o=1}^O (p_{s,t} - p_{o,t}) \times q_{o,t}}{q_t^{dev}} \quad (1)$$

$$q_t^{dev} = q_t^{down,dev} + q_t^{up,dev} \quad (2)$$

$$p_t^{down} = -(p_{s,t} - p_t^{pen}) \quad (3)$$

$$p_t^{up} = p_{s,t} + p_t^{pen} \quad (4)$$

where:

- (i) $p_{s,t}$ is the spot price of the scheduled dispatch;
- (ii) $p_{o,t}$ and $q_{o,t}$ are the price and quantity of the balancing mechanisms o considering all balancing mechanisms O ;
- (iii) q_t^{dev} is the total quantity of imbalanced energy;
- (iv) p_t^{pen} is the penalty value;
- (v) p_t^{down} and p_t^{up} are the downward and upward imbalance prices, respectively;
- (vi) $q_t^{down,dev}$, $q_t^{up,dev}$ are the total quantities of energy deviated by BRPs in down and up directions, respectively.

The penalty is negative when upward and down balancing prices are lower and higher than spot prices, respectively. In this case BRPs are penalized. Otherwise, if the penalty is positive they are compensated. The penalty can be positive depending if the cash-flow between the costs of deviations from spot markets minus balancing energy costs is positive. BRPs receive/pay the imbalance prices, which corresponds to the difference between the spot and the balancing prices. BRPs with upward deviations are injecting more energy than scheduled, receiving the sum of the spot price with the penalty (upward imbalance price). Therefore, if the penalty is higher than the spot price they will have a cost for the extra injected energy. BRPs with down deviations receive the subtraction of the penalty with the spot price (downward deviation price). If the deviation prices are positive, TSOs have to pay to BRPs. Otherwise, BRPs pay to TSOs.

The Nordpool and Spanish mechanisms compute the balance direction and only the BRPs that originate those balance needs must directly pay the price of the energy used to balance the system [13], [16]. Contrary to the Portuguese, this mechanism considers double penalties and single pricing (presented in equations 5–7) [15], [17].

$$p_t^{down} = -(p_{s,t} - p_t^{down,pen}) \quad (6)$$

$$p_t^{up} = p_{s,t} + p_t^{up,pen} \quad (7)$$

where:

- (i) $p_t^{down,pen}$ and $p_t^{up,pen}$ are the penalties of downwards and upward deviations, respectively;
- (ii) $q_{o,t}^{down}$ and $q_{o,t}^{up}$ are the quantities of energy used by mechanism o for downwards and upward balance, respectively.

When the downward balancing energy is higher than the upward, only BRPs with net up deviation pay penalties. On the contrary, when the upward balancing energy is higher, only net down deviations are paid. The problem with this mechanism is that only net deviations in the dominant direction are paid. So, it highly increases the paid penalties by BRPs with net deviations [15], [16]. However, contrary to the Portuguese imbalance settlement, it incentivizes unbalanced players to balance themselves (for more details check [14]).

Against this background, it is presented an alternative, the “Separated” IS, which consists of BRPs paying/receiving directly the costs/revenues of the balancing mechanisms needed to balance them, presented in the following formulations:

$$p_t^{up,pen} = \frac{\sum_{o=1}^O (p_{s,t} - p_{o,t}^{down}) \times q_{o,t}^{down}}{q_t^{down,dev}} \quad (8)$$

$$p_t^{down,pen} = \frac{\sum_{o=1}^O (p_{o,t}^{up} - p_{s,t}) \times q_{o,t}^{up}}{q_t^{up,dev}} \quad (9)$$

The proposed mechanism consists of double pricing presented in Equations 6 and 7 and double penalties presented in Equations 8 and 9. In this mechanism, the net cost/revenues of TSOs with energy balancing mechanisms are zero. It is a fair system that considers the direct payment of upward and downward energy balancing by up and down unbalanced

$$penalties = \begin{cases} p_t^{up,pen} = 0 & \text{if } \sum_{o=1}^O q_{o,t}^{up} < \sum_{o=1}^O q_{o,t}^{down} \\ p_t^{up,pen} = \min \left[\frac{\sum_{o=1}^O (p_{o,t}^{down} - p_{s,t}) \times q_{o,t}^{down}}{\sum_{o=1}^O q_{o,t}^{down}}, 0 \right] & \text{if } \sum_{o=1}^O q_{o,t}^{up} \leq \sum_{o=1}^O q_{o,t}^{down} \\ p_t^{down,pen} = 0 & \text{if } \sum_{o=1}^O q_{o,t}^{up} > \sum_{o=1}^O q_{o,t}^{down} \\ p_t^{down,pen} = \min \left[\frac{\sum_{o=1}^O (p_{s,t} - p_{o,t}^{up}) \times q_{o,t}^{up}}{\sum_{o=1}^O q_{o,t}^{up}}, 0 \right] & \text{if } \sum_{o=1}^O q_{o,t}^{up} \geq \sum_{o=1}^O q_{o,t}^{down} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

BRPs, respectively. Furthermore, by separating the payment of penalties between unbalance directions, this mechanism also incentivizes BRPs to self-control their dispatch, mitigating part of their deviations.

Each period, t , balance responsibility of BRPs, C_t^{dev} , considering their deviations, q_t^{dev} and the prices of the excess or lack of electricity, in cases of up, p_t^{up} , or down, p_t^{down} deviations, respectively:

$$\begin{cases} C_t^{dev} = q_t^{dev} P_t^{up}, & \text{for } q_t^{dev} > 0 \\ C_t^{dev} = |q_t^{dev}| P_t^{down}, & \text{for } q_t^{dev} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The levelized deviation cost, C^{dev} , is levelized by each period deviated energy, as follows:

$$C^{dev} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T C_t^{dev} \times q_t^{dev}}{\sum_{t=1}^T q_t^{dev}} \quad (11)$$

The open-access REStade tool comprises the models of the aforementioned three mechanisms. REStade has been used to evaluate the output of IS mechanisms in the following case studies.

IV. CASE STUDIES

This section presents the outcomes of two case-studies. Case study I considers the simulation of each IS during 2019 in Portugal and Spain using real-data³. Case study II focuses on the costs incurred by an active Portuguese CEC for each IS during 2019.

A. Case study I - Effect of different IS mechanisms in Portugal and Spain during 2019

The open-access version of the coupled tools REStade and MASCEM in Spine Toolbox was used to run MIBEL and the Portuguese and Spanish balancing markets in 2019. This study computes the average and levelized prices that BRPs have to pay for their imbalances (for more details check [25]). Table I presents the main results of the simulation.

Analysing Table I it can be concluded that in Portugal and Spain, BRPs pay around 13% and 21% of the wholesale market price for penalties. The Spanish balancing costs are lower, but in Spain, only net deviations are paid, while in Portugal, all BRPs pay for their deviations, which decreases the paid penalties. Using REStade is possible to compute

³Portuguese data is available at <https://mercado.ren.pt/EN/Electr/MarketInfo/>. Spanish data is available at <https://www.esios.ree.es/en/market-and-prices>

TABLE I
AVERAGE PRICES OF THE WHOLESALE AND BALANCING MARKETS.

Price €/MWh	DAM Price	Down IS Price	Up IS Price	Levelized IS Penalty
Portugal	47.73	49.54	45.91	6.12
Spain	47.68	51.53	43.18	10.19

the costs of the three IS mechanisms in Portugal and Spain during 2019. Tables II and III present the levelized and average penalties of the three studied mechanisms per country, respectively.

TABLE II
LEVELIZED PENALTIES WITH EACH IS MECHANISM.

Levelized penalty €/MWh	Portuguese	Spanish	Separated
Portugal	6.12	17.01	6.12
Spain	2.19	10.19	2.19

Analysing Table II can be concluded that the levelized penalty is the same in the Portuguese and the Separated mechanisms because it is the value that BRPs pay to TSOs. So, as in these two mechanisms, the cash flow of the TSO is zero and the levelized value is the same. It is worth to mention the value is substantially higher considering the Spanish mechanism. Furthermore, because only Spanish BRPs with net deviations pay, even paying more they only pay 88% of the costs of balancing energy. The negative cash flow of TSOs is then reflected in the tariffs paid by end-use consumers. Table III presents the average penalties of the three mechanisms.

TABLE III
AVERAGE PENALTIES WITH EACH IS MECHANISM.

Average penalty €/MWh	Portuguese	Spanish	Separated
Portugal	6.30	15.07	7.62
Spain	2.08	8.21	1.82

Analysing Tables I, II, and III can be concluded that the simulation of the Separated mechanism during 2019 in Portugal and Spain, resulted in an average penalty of 15.2% and 3.6% (the relative value of dividing the penalty by the wholesale price) of the wholesale prices paid by the Portuguese and Spanish BRPs, respectively. Notably, there was a 16% reduction in the weight of the penalty paid by the Spanish

BRPs, mainly by considering that all BRPs pay penalties. The increase of 2% in the weight of the penalties paid by Portuguese BRPs can be attributed to the separate payment of reserves required by each BRP to balance its deviations.

B. Case study II - Effect of different IS mechanisms on the remuneration of active market players

This case study verifies the effect of each IS mechanism in a citizen energy community (CEC) consisting of 312 real-world consumers who want to be active market players, representing 5% of the Portuguese demand during 2019 (for more details check [14])⁴. This CEC has a peak demand of 446 MW and none generation assets, being its regulated tariff in 2019 equal to 111.93 €/MWh (excluding VAT, the energy part is 70.68 €/MWh).

This study considers the active participation of the CEC in the wholesale market during 2019, bidding at the day-ahead and intraday markets, and paying the penalties defined by the IS mechanisms. Using the strategic bidding process for CECs presented in [14], and its forecast accuracy, the market outcomes and the leveled costs are presented in Table IV.

TABLE IV
LEVELIZED WHOLESALE ENERGY COSTS FOR EACH IS MECHANISM

Levelized costs €/MWh	Portuguese	Spanish	Separated
IS	1.50	1.42	1.39
Total	72.61	72.53	72.50

Analyzing Table IV is possible to conclude that consumers may reduce their costs by around 35% from 111.93 €/MWh to less than 73 €/MWh by being an active market player. These savings derived from a reduction of around 30% in the energy cost from 70.68 €/MWh to 47.39 €/MWh and in the CECs' grid access discount of 45% provided by the regulator (check [4] for more details). Also, the average cost of the imbalances weighs around 3% of the total energy cost, being slightly lower in the Separated IS mechanism.

Compared with the average penalties paid in Portugal and Spain, this active player pays between 75% and 92% less penalties compared with the penalty costs in Table III, respectively. In conclusion, IS mechanisms that incentivize self-balancing are important to increase the investment in self-consumption and storage capacity, increasing the flexibility and pro-activity of typically unbalanced demand-side and variable renewable players. Furthermore, by increasing their flexibility these players may increase their market outcomes.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented the "Separated" imbalance settlement (IS) mechanism aiming at incentive self-balancing and contributing to a neutral cash flow between IS penalties and balancing market costs. It was compared with the double

⁴The real consumption dataset of the consumers can be found in an online repository in https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/ElectricityLoadDiagrams20112_014#

pricing and single penalty Portuguese and the single pricing and penalty Spanish mechanisms using REStTrade tool.

The Portuguese mechanism considers that all the energy balancing costs or revenues are passed to the Balance Responsible Parties (BRPs), originating lower penalties when compared with the Spanish mechanism. However, it does not incentivize unbalanced parties to balance themselves because they can be compensated for their imbalances. In the Spanish mechanism, only those contributing to deviations in the dominant direction may pay penalties. Also, unbalanced parties are not compensated independently of the balancing prices, which may originate an economic surplus for Transmission System Operators (TSOs). However, when the costs of balancing the system in the dominant direction are lower than in the non-dominant direction, TSOs may have an economic deficit, which occurred in 2019, when the Spanish TSO had a economic deficit of 12% of the balancing costs, which is then reflected in the tariffs of consumers.

The Separated IS proposed in this work ensure that the value paid by BRPs for their deviations is equal to what TSOs pay to the players supporting balancing mechanisms. This mechanism considers double pricing and penalties, which means that BRPs have different prices and penalties according to their unbalanced direction. It considers that BRPs shall directly pay the cost of their unbalances to the players used to balance them, with TSOs acting only as intermediaries.

Results from two case studies demonstrate the benefit of using this mechanism to reduce penalties, mainly in the case of active market players. Analysing the country-wise results from 2019 is possible to verify that unbalanced parties in Portugal and Spain have penalties around 13.2% and 20.3% of the wholesale market price, respectively. In Spain, penalties are higher because are only paid by BRPs with net deviations. However, if it uses the Separated IS the weight of their penalties is reduced to 4.3%.

Future work will explore the effect of different IS mechanisms in the penalties paid by different inflexible and flexible players, such as wind, solar PV or hybrid power plants, retailers, consumers, and communities.

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REFERENCES

- [1] F. Lopes and H. Coelho, "Electricity Markets with Increasing Levels of Renewable Generation: Structure, Operation, Agent-Based Simulation and Emerging Designs", Springer, Cham, Switzerland, vol. 144, 2017.
- [2] H. Algarvio, F. Lopes, A. Couto, J. Santana and A. Estanqueiro, "Effects of Regulating the European Internal Market on the integration of Variable Renewable Energy", *WIREs: Energy Environ.* vol. 8(6),e346, 2019.
- [3] G. Strbac et al. "Decarbonization of Electricity Systems in Europe: Market Design Challenges", *IEEE Power and Energy Magazine* vol. 19(1), pp. 53–63, 2021.
- [4] H. Algarvio, "The Role of Local Citizen Energy Communities in the Road to Carbon-Neutral Power Systems: Outcomes from a Case Study in Portugal", *Smart Cities* vol. 4(2), pp. 840–863, 2021.

- [5] H. Algarvio, F. Lopes, A. Couto, A. Estanqueiro and J. Santana, "Variable Renewable Energy and Market Design: New Market Products and a Real-world Study", *Energies* vol. 12, 4576, 2019.
- [6] J. Prol, K. Steininger and D Zilberman, "The cannibalization effect of wind and solar in the California wholesale electricity market", *Energy Econ.* vol. 85, 104552, 2020.
- [7] H. Algarvio, "Risk-Sharing Contracts and risk management of bilateral contracting in electricity markets", *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.* vol. 144, 108579, 2023.
- [8] M. Bohland and S. Schwenen, Renewable support and strategic pricing in electricity markets. *Int. J. Ind. Organ.* vol. 80, 102792, 2022.
- [9] W. Hinderks and A. Wagner, "Factor models in the German electricity market: Stylized facts, seasonality, and calibration", *Energy Econ.* vol. 85, 104351, 2020.
- [10] T. Matsumoto, D. Bunn and Y. Yamada, "Mitigation of the inefficiency in imbalance settlement designs using day-ahead prices", *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 37(5), pp. 3333–3345, 2021.
- [11] T. Haring, D. Kirschen, and G. Andersson, "Incentive compatible imbalance settlement", *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 30(6), pp. 3338–3346, 2015.
- [12] P. Frade, J. Pereira, J. Santana and J. Catalão, "Wind balancing costs in a power system with high wind penetration—Evidence from Portugal", *Energy Policy*, vol. 132, pp. 702–713, 2019.
- [13] H. Holttinen, J. Miettinen, A. Couto, H. Algarvio and L. Rodrigues, "Wind power producers in shorter gate closure markets and balancing markets", in 13th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM16), p. 5, 2016.
- [14] H. Algarvio, "Strategic Participation of Active Citizen Energy Communities in Spot Electricity Markets Using Hybrid Forecast Methodologies", *Eng* vol. 4, pp. 1–14, 2022.
- [15] S. Martín-Martínez, A. Lorenzo-Bonache, A. Honrubia-Escribano, M. Cañas-Carretón and E. Gómez-Lázaro, "Contribution of wind energy to balancing markets: The case of Spain", *WIREs: Energy Environ.*, vol. 7(5), e300, 2018.
- [16] A. Khodadadi, L. Herre, P. Shinde, R. Eriksson, L. Söder and M. Amelin, "Nordic balancing markets: Overview of market rules", in 17th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM20), p. 6, 2020.
- [17] J. Bottieau, L. Hubert, Z. De Grève, F. Vallée and J. Toubreau, "Very-short-term probabilistic forecasting for a risk-aware participation in the single price imbalance settlement" *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 35(2), pp. 1218–1230, 2019.
- [18] I. Praça, C. Ramos, Z. Vale and M. Cordeiro, MASCEM: a multiagent system that simulates competitive electricity markets. *IEEE Intelligent Systems*, vol. 18(6), pp. 54–60, 2003.
- [19] D. Kirschen and G. Strbac, "Fundamentals of Power System Economics", Wiley, Chichester, UK, 2018.
- [20] H. Algarvio, "Multi-step optimization of the purchasing options of power retailers to feed their portfolios of consumers", *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 142, 108260, 2022.
- [21] H. Nordström *et al.*, "Strategies for Continuous Balancing in Future Power Systems with High Wind and Solar Shares", *Energies*, vol. 16, 5249, 2023.
- [22] H. Algarvio, F. Lopes, A. Couto and A. Estanqueiro, "Participation of wind power producers in day-ahead and balancing markets: An overview and a simulation-based study", *WIREs: Energy Environ.*, vol. 8(5), e343, 2019.
- [23] P. Frade, M. Shafie-khah, J. Santana and J. Catalão, "Cooperation in ancillary services: Portuguese strategic perspective on replacement reserves", *Energy Strategy Reviews* vol. 23, pp. 142–151, 2019.
- [24] P. Frade, G. Osório, J. Santana and J. Catalão, "Cooperation Regional coordination in ancillary services: An innovative study for secondary control in the Iberian electrical system", *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems* vol. 109, pp. 513–525, 2019.
- [25] A. Estanqueiro *et al.*, "D 5.3 Performance assessment of current and new market designs and trading mechanisms for national and regional markets", Project report, 2022 [Online]. Available: https://traderes.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/D5.3_TradeRES_PerformanceAssessmentMarkets.pdf.